

Inclusive Futures for the National Federation of Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs): Exploring Power Dynamics and Epistemic Cultures

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Executive summary

What is the “Inclusive Futures” project?

This report is part of the project *Inclusive Futures: User Cultural Narratives and Mapping Pathways for NFCS*, whose aim was to explore how federated Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs), such as National Federated Compute Services, shape scientific collaboration and culture. The project lasted from August 2025 to July 2026, and it was funded by NetworkPlus – a new UKRI-funded initiative (EPSRC) aimed at strengthening collaboration and knowledge exchange between researchers, service providers, and stakeholders. The inclusive futures project aimed to 1) identify the cultural and epistemic challenges that hinder the national federation of DRIs, and 2) collaboratively develop pathways for more inclusive community building and governance, which can inform the NFCS roadmaps.

What problem is addressed?

The national coordination of DRIs has become essential for supporting investments in large-scale computing, both at the exascale level and in AI. However, this work is inherently interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral. A critical challenge lies in bridging communities with distinctive *epistemic cultures* – i.e., diverse ways of knowing, reasoning, and doing – as power relations across disciplines and sectors are reorganised and digital infrastructures and technologies repurposed. Therefore, this report focused on identifying the social, cultural, epistemic and institutional tensions that need to be considered when designing and developing the national federation of DRIs.

How is the problem approached?

The project focused on the relationship of *power relations* and *epistemic cultures* as new users and sector seek to join federated DRIs. Drawing on a sociological perspective, the project conceptualised the DRI as a *social system* that becomes institutionalised by drawing *boundaries* between itself and its environment – the wider research and innovation ecosystem. As such, the DRI survives by *reducing complexity* of the environment through selective filtering of what it can process. Consequently, federated DRI develops their own “social and cultural codes”, which define how they differentiate themselves from other systems (Lamont & Molnár, 2002).

However, these codes and norms are not developed in isolation; they are embedded within a web of power relations and shaped by a contested landscape of epistemic cultures. Thus, who holds power within a social system controls the “filtering process”. For example, the

High-Performance Computing (HPC) community operates with its own distinctive codes, which shape key aspects of the DRI system. Because of this, the HPC community holds a position of power within the DRI landscape that can make it difficult for the DRI system to integrate the diversity and complexity of epistemic cultures seeking to join the system.

The integration (inclusion) of new users and communities – according to some sociological theories – depends on the existence of what can be described as “stabilised interfaces” – i.e., institutionalised coupling arrangements (durable) that make communication across boundaries repeatable and reliably connectable without requiring full consensus or a shared worldview (Lamont & Molnár, 2002). For instance, universities couple science and education, enabling coordination between systems while preserving each system’s internal logic. This form of “coupling” facilitates interaction without full integration. In other words, it is about structures and mechanisms designed for building epistemic trust among epistemically differentiated cultures.

Yet inclusion also depends on “destabilised interfaces” – non-institutional arrangements through which cross-boundary collaboration remains emergent, contingent, and structurally conflictual. Interfaces such as “alignment work”, “resistance practices”, and “trading zones” operate as flexible practices and spaces that can be tailored to specific communities while still supporting intelligibility across communities. Crucially, these interfaces are continuously negotiated and renegotiated within and across communities (Bowker & Star, 1999; Star & Griesemer, 1989).

This conceptual framework was used to explore the social, cultural, epistemic, and institutional tensions emerging from the federation of DRIs. Empirically, the study combined a survey with semi-structured interviews involving active, potential, and inactive DRI users across academia, the public sector, and industry – a comparative framework. The survey mapped competing imaginaries, values, and practices associated with DRI federation, while the interviews examined current and future tensions, with particular attention to the challenges of developing nationally federated DRIs.

What are the results?

The combined results from the survey and interviews are six tensions along two axes. The power axis includes tensions between *centralisation* and *decentralisation*, *invisibility* and *visibility*, and *privacy* and *surveillance*. The epistemic axis includes tensions between *empowerment* and *disempowerment*, *uncertainty* and *certainty*, and *unity* and *disunity*. These six tensions are accompanied with user narratives (from active, potential and inactive users) that highlight existing and future barriers to DRI national federation, as well

as the social, cultural, epistemic and institutional conditions that may enable its development.

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1. Introduction: Power Dynamics and Epistemic Cultures in the National Federation of Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs)

Researchers, professionals and practitioners across academia, the public sector and industry who deal with different types of data increasingly rely on large-scale computing infrastructures to collaborate, share data, and generate new knowledge. With large investments being made into large-scale computing, both at an exascale level and for AI, its national coordination has become crucial. The federation of Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs) – e.g., High-Performance Computing, Trusted Research Environments (TREs), AI systems, etc. – seeks to enable coherent and streamlined access for diverse user communities to existing and newly provisioned compute services and resources.

However, a critical challenge lies in bringing together communities with distinctive *epistemic cultures* – i.e., diverse ways of knowing, communicating, reasoning, and doing (Knorr-Cetina, 1999). These cultural differences shape how they navigate and respond to changes in they work, making it difficult to anticipate and plan how different type of users – active, potential and inactive – will respond to the efforts to expand and consolidate the federation of DRIs (Littlejohn et al., 2026).

The literature highlights that changes in the workplace driven by digital technologies may create new forms of *boundary work* – work needed to maintain and create new distinctions between groups and to protect existing or acquire new practices (Langley et al., 2019); and *boundary objects* – abstract or material objects that make cross-boundary communication possible over time, such as governance mechanisms, trust frameworks, onboarding rules, standards, digital interfaces, etc (Star & Griesemer 1989; Bowker & Star, 1999). These boundaries may vary across sectors and disciplines, making it difficult to create the conditions for interoperability, communication and collaboration. The reorganisation of these conditions may create new inclusion/exclusion dynamics and thereby inhibit/enable the federation of DRIs.

From a social science perspective, what is at stake is the reconfiguration of power dynamics and the role of epistemic cultures in shaping the practices, values, and expectations linked to the federation of DRIs. As a result, some fundamental questions arise: Who determines access to federated DRIs? Who is able to thrive, who is excluded, and which ways of reasoning and epistemic practices are valued and devalued? These are, at their core, questions about *power relations* and about the inclusion and exclusion of different *epistemic cultures* within national DRI federations.

The social sciences have long addressed such issues across diverse contexts, offering valuable insights to better understand these power dynamics and act on them. A key example is STS, an approach that has often been explicitly normative and interventionist, particularly since the 1990s. STS scholars frequently advocate greater participation in shaping sociotechnical futures. This stance draws on the idea that science and technology are co-produced with society (Jasanoff, 2004), implying a responsibility to contribute to the design, development, and deployment of more inclusive and reflexive systems. Likewise, critical infrastructure studies have explored emerging forms of power dynamics and contestation within communication infrastructures (Jansen et al., 2026), as well as how new modes of interactivity and training raise new concerns related to data circulation, science communication, and human and non-human interaction (Halpern, 2015).

Drawing on a social science perspective, including sociology of scientific knowledge, STS, among others, we argue that the analysis of the role of new power relations and epistemic cultures in shaping research and innovation is essential to understanding the social and cultural dimension of the federation of DRIs. This is relevant because power is not simply an oppressive force that is exercised through top-down structures; it is also a mode of relating to oneself and others – *power relations*. Power circulates through everyday practices, often in subtle or elusive ways. Examining epistemic cultures through the lens of power relations therefore involves recognising how certain disciplines, epistemologies and ways of reasoning reproduce or reinforce inequalities in ways that are often difficult to identify and recognise.

The debate about power and culture is not new but it is reinvigorated by the debates in academic and policy circles about the national federation of DRIs. This broader lens provides a starting point for analysing the future of DRI federation.

2. A sociological approach to DRI federation

The study employs a sociological approach that conceptualises DRI through two complementary perspectives. On the one hand, DRI is seen as a *social system* that becomes institutionalised – e.g., federated – by drawing *boundaries* between itself and its environment – i.e., the wider research and innovation ecosystem. As a social system, the DRI develops and survives by *reducing complexity* of the environment through selective filtering of what it can process. Consequently, DRI develops their own “codes” and “norms” (operational closure), which define how they differentiate themselves from other systems. The integration of new communities depends on the existence of what can be described as “(de)stabilised interfaces” – institutionalised and non-institutionalised coupling arrangements that make communication across boundaries repeatable and reliably

connectable without requiring full consensus or a shared worldview – stabilised interfaces such as standards, guidelines, ontologies and shared classification systems, or what Star and Griesemer (1989) called “boundary objects”; destabilised interfaces such as “alignment work” (Kruse & Silvast, 2023) and “trading zones” (Galison, 1997; Gorman, 2010).

On the other hand, the DRI is seen as a *site of epistemic transformation* in which power relations are continually reorganised, redistributed and renegotiated by the inclusion and exclusion of different user communities. Thus, federation is a *cultural practice* and *socio-technical arrangement* that involves three interrelated dimensions: objects (data, tools, infrastructures), knowledge (skills and competencies required to use HPC), and practices (the enactment – current or anticipated – of federation).

These perspectives point to something crucial when addressing DRI federation: *plurality creates a coordination problem*. If epistemic cultures differ, the key question then is what allows them to collaborate and exchange without dissolving into confusion or forcing homogenisation? What “destabilised interfaces” – or boundary work – can support the federation of DRIs beyond standards, guidelines, ontologies, and shared classification systems? A sociological approach assumes that users’ ways of reasoning, perceptions and imaginaries are situated within dense cultural configurations and embedded power relations that influence what users perceive as possible, desirable, or legitimate.

3. Research questions

In the context of new power dynamics, the unbalance influence of different epistemic cultures and shifting epistemic practices because of new digital technologies, the following questions were addressed to explore the challenges around the federation of DRIs:

- What social, cultural, epistemic and institutional challenges and tensions are emerging within the DRI ecosystem as its national federation is negotiated, and how might these impede its implementation?
- How do different types of users of federated DRI perceive these challenges, and how do they envision the conditions needed for an inclusive federated DRI ecosystem?

4. Methods

To explore the shifting power dynamics and the social and cultural challenges involved in bringing together different epistemic cultures, the study employed a mixed-methods approach. A national survey was distributed to users to investigate how and why they engage with federated DRIs – or why they choose not to. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted to examine users’ perceptions, experiences, and expectations

around the national federation of DRIs. To support this analysis, a comparative framework was developed to explore these issues across different user archetypes and sectors.

4.1. Comparative framework: active, potential and inactive users across academia, public and private sectors

Drawing on the scoping review and feedback from the NetworkPlus NFCS, we developed a comparative framework to examine the perceptions, experiences, and expectations of different types of users of federated DRIs. The first distinction is between active, potential, and inactive users. By differentiating users according to their level of engagement and their capacity to participate in federated DRIs, we were able to analyse more effectively the challenges related to inclusion. The diagram below illustrates this distinction:

Figure 1. User groups by level of engagement

The diagram positions participants along two dimensions: actual engagement (y-axis) and capacity or opportunity for engagement (x-axis). Inactive users have low awareness and no current engagement. Potential users have the interest or capacity to engage in the

future but are not yet active. Active users are currently engaged in the design, development, or use of federated infrastructures. The diagram further highlights that user engagement is *dynamic* rather than fixed, shaped by a range of temporal factors. Attending to this temporality is key to a broader understanding of inclusion in DRI federation. Based on these user archetypes, an *inclusive* model of national federated DRIs is understood as the establishment of the social, cultural, epistemic and institutional conditions that enable recognition of epistemic cultures in ways that improve inclusion over time.

The second distinction relates to users situated in the academic, public, and private sectors. This differentiation enabled a more nuanced analysis of how institutional settings influence the challenges users experience. Access-related issues encountered by academic users differ from those faced by users in public and private organisations. The composition of the survey and interview samples also varied across sectors. These distinctions are detailed in the next sections.

In summary, this comparative approach is essential for understanding the complexities involved in developing a more inclusive model of DRI federation. It makes visible how each sector comprises a mix of active, potential, and inactive users, each with different levels of engagement, capabilities, and barriers to participation. Recognising these differentiated user groups allows us to identify where inclusion efforts are falling short and what forms of support or intervention are needed to enable more participation across the federated landscape.

4.2. Survey

Surveys are particularly well-suited for mapping diversity of perspectives across dispersed populations, which is essential in the case of federated DRIs spanning multiple sectors, disciplines, and geographies within the UK.

The survey was designed to explore how different users from academia, public sector and industry imagine, value, and engage with federated DRIs. Given the diversity of DRIs, the survey was designed as an exploratory instrument to capture not only actual practices but also broader imaginaries (expectations and assumptions) and values (normative commitments and priorities). A mixed-format survey (closed and open questions) was used to allow for both comparability across respondents and the capture of unexpected or emergent perspectives.

The survey was structured around four analytical dimensions – imaginaries, values, practices, and skills – informed by a diverse literature, particularly insights from social studies of science:

- **Imaginaries:** exploring expectations and visions of what DRI federation is and should become. This dimension draws on work in STS on sociotechnical imaginaries (Jasanoff & Kim, 2009), capturing how infrastructures are envisioned to shape future research and innovation practices and governance.
- **Values:** investigating what principles respondents see as important or currently supported in DRIs (e.g., openness, equity, sovereignty). This follows traditions in the history of science and ethics of technology that link infrastructural development to epistemic and normative commitments (Daston & Galison, 2007).
- **Practices:** identifying concrete forms of engagement or non-engagement with DRIs. This dimension situates infrastructures in everyday research and innovation work, focusing on barriers and opportunities.
- **Skills:** exploring concrete gaps in skills that are needed to DRI federation. This dimension emphasises the human aspect of the development of digital technologies and infrastructures.

These dimensions provide a holistic understanding of federated DRIs that goes beyond purely technical adoption studies and incorporates ethical, cultural, and political dimensions.

Question types and rationale:

- Closed multiple-choice and Likert-scale questions were used to measure imaginaries, values, and practices in a way that enables quantitative comparison across groups, disciplines, and sectors.
- Open-ended questions were included to capture unanticipated discourses and meanings that may not fit predefined categories.
- Matrix-style Likert items reduce survey fatigue while ensuring coverage of key themes (e.g., values).

The survey was designed to take 10-15 minutes to maximise completion rates while ensuring sufficient coverage. Language was kept accessible across disciplinary and sectoral boundaries to avoid privileging specific technical or academic vocabularies.

The survey was distributed between October 2025 and January 2026 through different routes:

- Email lists: Jisc digital research community list, Research Data Management discussion list and the Public discussion list for Collaborative Computational Projects for Arts, Humanities and Culture (CCP-AHC).
- Workshops and conferences: NFCS conferences (2025) and DRI congress (2025)

50 people responded the survey. This number may seem low; however, it is important to note that many participants were experiencing ‘survey fatigue’ due to the multiple questionnaires distributed by the NetworkPlus projects. The tables below provide more details about survey respondents (some respondents didn’t respond to all the questions):

Area	Number of respondents	%
Academia	27	57.44%
Public sector	4	8.5%
Industry	16	34.04%
Total	47	100%

Table 1. Respondents by area

Gender	Number of respondents	%
Female	15	50%
Male	14	46.7%
Preferred not to say	1	3.3%
Total	30	100%

Table 2. Respondents by gender

Type of user	Number of respondents	%
Active user	24	52.2%
Potential user	15	32.6%
Inactive user	7	15.2%
Total	46	100%

Table 3. Respondents by type of user (self-identification)

4.3. Interviews

Drawing on previous literature (Durán del Fierro & Littlejohn, 2025), the interviews were organised around issues of power, infrastructures/technologies, and epistemic cultures and practices. To capture the diversity of relationships that researchers and professionals have with federated DRIs, the study employed three different but parallel interview guides: for active, inactive, and potential users. Each group represents a different mode of engagement, which shapes the types of questions that were asked:

- For active users, the interview guide emphasises lived experiences, asking participants to reflect on how federated infrastructures have reshaped their practices, collaborations, and professional identities.
- For potential users, the interview guide explores motivations, expectations, and conditions for future adoption. It asks participants to imagine how federation might transform their work and to identify enablers or barriers to engagement.
- For inactive users, the interview guide focuses on barriers and alternatives, seeking to understand why individuals or communities remain disengaged, what practices they rely on instead, and what values or concerns underpin their stance.

While the overall structure of the interview guides remains coherent – covering experiences, perceptions of ‘federation’, challenges, practices, reflexive professional identity questions, and closing reflections – each guide was tailored to the specific engagement status of participants. This comparative design ensured both coherence across interviews (allowing thematic analysis across groups) and sensitivity to participants’ different positions vis-à-vis federated infrastructures. This enabled an analysis not only of how infrastructures are used and shaped but also of why they may be resisted, ignored, or anticipated.

The table below shows the similarities and differences between interview guides:

Section	Active users	Inactive users	Potential users
1. Introduction	Confirm understanding of project, answer questions from participant for clarification.	Same	Same
2. General questions – life histories/career and practices	Career path up to involvement in DRIs; first encounters and motivations.	Career path; current digital tools; whether they’ve heard of DRIs.	Career path; current tools; any exposure to DRIs (colleagues, projects, policies).
3. Meaning and perceptions	What “federation” means; values, principles, barriers;	What “federation” evokes; perceived values/risks;	What “federation” means; expectations and imagined benefits; concerns/uncertainties;

	how it reshapes collaboration/ ownership.	imagined benefits/drawbacks; possible impact on collaboration /ownership.	possible changes to collaboration/ ownership.
4. Practices	Examples of changed work practices due to DRI federation; technologies and communities involved; learning, tensions, benefits.	How they currently access/share/store data or use technologies for research; reasons for non-engagement (awareness, barriers, trust); alternative practices.	What conditions would enable adoption (training, support, incentives, compatibility); features that would attract them; scenarios of future use; challenges and risks.
Reflexive questions	How federation shaped identity, collaboration, relation to research artefacts; whether they proposed changes	How current practices shape identity, collaboration, relation to artefacts; what ideal infrastructure would look like	How engagement <i>might</i> reshape identity, collaboration, relation to artefacts; what ideal/desired infrastructure would look like
5. Closing	Anything missing? Questions for researcher.	Same	Same

Table 4. Interview guides by types of users

31 semi-structured interviews with different users (active, potential and inactive) across sectors (academia, industry and public sector) were conducted online between October 2025 and January 2026. The sample was predominantly male, comprising 23 men and 8 women. The table below provides more details about participants:

	Area/ sector	Number	Type of user	Research council
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1.	Academia / digital humanities	7	Active / potential	AHRC
2.	Public sector / cultural heritage	3	Inactive	AHRC
3.	Public sector / HPC facility	2	Active	EPSRC / STFC
4.	Public sector / research organisation	1	Active	EPSRC / STFC
5.	NHS and adjacent organisations	6	Potential	MRC
6.	Government / local and central	3	Inactive	N/A
7.	Infrastructure providers	2	Active	BBSRC / NERC
8.	Industry / small-size	5	Active / Potential	N/A
9.	Industry / medium-large size	2	Active / Potential	N/A

Table 5. Interviewees by categories

Automatic transcripts were generated using Microsoft Teams’ built-in transcription tool. These transcripts were then carefully reviewed and manually cleaned to preserve the meaning of participants’ responses. Interviews were analysed thematically, without the use of AI tools. The thematic analysis involved developing a coding system from which sub-themes were generated, followed by the identification of overarching themes. This process is iterative and continual. The final themes were produced at the intersection of sociological theory and the empirical data.

5. Social, Cultural and Epistemic Challenges to DRI Federation in the UK

5.1. An overview of imaginaries, practices and values around DRI federation

The survey provided a general overview of how different types of users (active, potential and inactive) perceive the development of a national federated DRI ecosystem.

Imaginarities

What is a “federated DRI ecosystem”? Users have differing interpretations of what federation means. When presented with alternative definitions, 41.3% of respondents selected “technical system” to describe what federation of DRIs is, followed by 32.6% who chose “collaborative ecosystem”, and 15.2% who selected “governance framework”. While these elements are complementary rather than mutually exclusive, the results suggest there is no shared understanding of what federation entails, or at least which aspect is considered most central.

When asked what federated DRIs should look like in the next 10 years, these differing views were confirmed. Below some examples:

- “...not confined to specific academic and technical elites; taking a “true” federate form”
- “**Sustainability** should be central to their design”
- “...should prioritize independence from Big Tech”
- “**Security and privacy** must be foundational, with strong **data governance** frameworks that protect sensitive research data while enabling collaboration across institutional boundaries”
- “The goal is infrastructure that is **sovereign, sustainable, secure**, and genuinely serves the research community rather than commercial interests”
- “simple, easy and impactful”
- “**democratising access** should be a priority and the development of the collaborative ecosystem is the most important thing”
- “A system that **unifies people, processes and technology** across the matrix of disciplinary and institutional boundaries.”
- “**integrated networks of repositories**, with metadata harmonised (probably with AI) with readily available systems for ingestion of new material, including licensing and access considerations.”

- “A collaborative network of shared resources with a democratic system of sharing and ownership”
- “automated as much as possible”

Values

When asked to assess the importance of various values in the development and deployment of federated compute services, respondents reported the following, ranked from most important to least important (1 is “not at all important” and 5 is “extremely important”):

Variable	Count	Average	Median	
Democratic decision-making p...	45	2.60	3	
Openness and transparency	46	1.74	2	
Flexibility	45	2.27	2	
Inclusivity and diversity (recog...	46	1.72	2	
Collaboration and cooperation	45	1.71	2	
Data sovereignty and local co...	46	1.83	2	
Efficiency and speed of access	46	2.11	2	
Reliability and technical robus...	46	1.54	1	
Interoperability across system...	46	1.52	1	
Trust and accountability in go...	46	1.67	1	
Total (10)	457	1.87		

In this context, when asked which of these values are currently well-supported in existing federated systems, respondents reported the following:

Q8: Based...ted Choice	Checked Percent	Check...Count	Sample Size
Collaboration and cooperation		38.2%	13 / 34
Openness and transparency		26.5%	9 / 34
Reliability and robustness		26.5%	9 / 34
Trust and accountability		26.5%	9 / 34
Data sovereignty		23.5%	8 / 34
Efficiency		17.6%	6 / 34
Inclusivity and diversity		14.7%	5 / 34
Interoperability		14.7%	5 / 34
Other		11.8%	4 / 34
Flexibility		11.8%	4 / 34
Democracy		0.0%	0 / 34

When asked if there any values or principles missing in the development of federated DRIs, respondents said the following:

- “Sustainability”
- “Equity of access, no matter the size of the organisation or availability/lack of availability of local support and guidance.”
- “Equality”
- “Ethics”
- “Fairness in how access and resources are distributed to different communities”
- “I’m not sure that the aspect of responsibility and good governance is properly represented by the current list”
- “The above values are well summarised. It is a matter to prioritise them and get them practising in the host organisations.
- “The above values are well summarised. It is a matter to prioritise them and get them practising in the host organisations.”
- “Environmental sustainability”

Practices

When asked which activities they would you like to engage in using federated Digital Research Infrastructures, respondents selected the following:

Q11: Which...ted Choice	Checked Percent	Check...Count	Sample Size
Accessing and analyzing data...		62.2%	28 / 45
Sharing my own data or resou...		57.8%	26 / 45
Using computational resource...		57.8%	26 / 45
Training or learning opportunit...		57.8%	26 / 45
Contributing to standards or p...		51.1%	23 / 45
Participating in governance or ...		46.7%	21 / 45
Other		8.9%	4 / 45

When asked which practices they think will be fundamentally altered by the federation of DRIs, respondents selected the following:

When asked what barriers may prevent users from engaging with federated DRIs, respondents selected the following:

Skills

When asked what skills users will have to learn to be part of federated DRIs, respondents selected the following:

When asked what skills or knowledge are lacking in community to fully benefit from federated DRIs, respondents shared the following (open question):

- “Simple awareness and the cost of access in terms of time and processes”.
- “Policy”

- “Awareness who can what for which reasons and how to access resources/infrastructure. I have ran workshops on this researcher awareness if poor but resources are also limited”
- “interoperability and data management skills”
- “Legal frameworks supported by the main data contributors and researchers that show an understanding/agreement of roles and responsibilities.”
- “Connecting with data I could use in my research”
- “The ability to communicating across disciplines”.
- “Vision! Leadership is too myopic to recognise the importance of DRIs”
- “I support Energy researchers and they come from a wide range of underpinning communities and domains and so I think framing questions around communities can cause issues in multi-disciplinary areas as it is more difficult to get consensus”
- “The governance skills and understanding of the complex, somewhat political landscapes”.
- “The technical skills needed to feel comfortable shifting analyses to these platforms”.
- “Data management skills, domain-specific knowledge, policy/legal/ethical knowledge”.
- “If communities need to learn a lot of new skills, federation has failed”.

When asked who should be responsible for providing training and skill development for federated DRIs, respondents selected the following:

Q30: In yo...ted Choice	Checked Percent	Check...Count	Sample Size
National infrastructure provide...		37	45
Individual institutions (universi...		25	45
Peers and communities of pra...		17	45
International federations and ...		15	45
Professional societies or asso...		11	45
Other		1	45

When asked what skills will become more important for engaging with federated DRIs in the next 5–10 years, respondents said the following (open question):

- “Secondary data skills”
- “Embedding within tools already used by researchers – e.g. search engines, generative AI tools, analytical software, modelling tools. The offerings also need to be clearly tailored for specific disciplines, recognising the types of data used and the tools required.”
- “Coding, data harmonisation, infrastructure provision”
- “Computational thinking and data informed decision making”

- “Governance and regulatory understanding.”
- “Disclosure control”
- “Issues around responsible AI, FAIR and CARE, changes in GDPR, etc”
- “Communication/translation.”
- “Coding, textual conversion, data visualisation, training for people outside of academia to get access”.
- “How AI is integrated with such tools”
- “AI and Data literacy.”
- “Data management, technical and AI, interoperability, data governance, cybersecurity, and collaboration”.
- “Data stewardship”.

5.2. Examples of social, cultural and epistemic controversies

The interviews revealed a range of challenges – or controversies – for the national federation of DRIs. These examples provide a framework for understanding the themes–tensions that organise the user narratives (see Section 6.3). The following eight examples are presented under two headings: “Context” and “Points of Friction”.

5.2.1. Example 1: Bridging HPC openness and sensitive data cultures

Context:

The national federation of DRIs will bring together communities with fundamentally different epistemic cultures. High-Performance Computing (HPC) communities have historically prioritised openness, transparency, and shared access to data and code. By contrast, researchers working with sensitive data – such as health, clinical, genomic, or certain collections data – operate under strict legal, ethical, and social mandates to protect privacy and maintain tight control of access.

Points of friction:

- HPC infrastructures often assume broad, standardised access policies, while health-data environments require highly granular, risk-based governance. These differences create uncertainty about who controls what, and under which legal or ethical frameworks.
- HPC practices favour open datasets to maximise computational value. Sensitive-data communities must minimise visibility – even to infrastructure

- operators – to comply with data-protection requirements. This creates tension over acceptable levels of transparency, metadata exposure, and oversight.
- Infrastructure designs often embed the values of one community (e.g., efficiency, openness) while neglecting others (e.g., safeguarding, proportionality, care). Researchers handling sensitive data may feel their values are marginalised in technical decision-making, leading to resistance or non-use.
 - When health researchers require HPC resources, questions arise about how to maintain ethical integrity – responsibility – within systems not originally built for privacy-sensitive contexts. Ambiguity around where ethical responsibility lies (researcher? institution? infrastructure provider?) creates hesitation and risk aversion.
 - HPC users may feel slowed or constrained by privacy requirements, while sensitive-data communities may feel disempowered by unfamiliar HPC processes, limited autonomy, or unclear safeguards. Unequal power dynamics can hinder collaboration.

5.2.2. Example 2: Evolving expectations among HPC users

Context:

Federated HPC infrastructures must increasingly support two distinct generations of research practice. Traditional HPC users rely on classic batch-scheduled workflows, while newer researchers – accustomed to cloud-native environments – expect interactive, containerised, and on-demand compute. These divergent expectations create a growing cultural and technical gap within national HPC ecosystems.

Points of friction:

- Classic HPC systems rely on schedulers such as Slurm and environment modules, whereas cloud-native workflows depend on Kubernetes, containers, and notebook servers. These tooling ecosystems are not naturally interoperable, creating integration challenges and forcing infrastructure providers to maintain parallel toolchains.
- Batch workflows are optimised for throughput and predictability but feel slow and restrictive to users accustomed to on-demand cloud experiences. Cloud-native workflows, while flexible, can disrupt the scheduling and resource-planning mechanisms that traditional HPC systems rely on. Balancing these approaches is technically and culturally challenging.
- New researchers may find traditional HPC environments inaccessible due to command-line complexity, environment-module management, or queue-based

execution models. Conversely, long-standing HPC practitioners may be unfamiliar or reluctant to adopt containers or notebook-centric workflows. This divergence in familiarity drives uneven adoption and resistance to change.

- Traditional HPC users tend to prioritise maximum performance, efficient scheduling, and system utilisation. Cloud-native users tend to prioritise usability, interactivity, and fast start-up times. These priorities can be in tension: mechanisms that enhance user convenience may reduce system efficiency, while performance-optimised systems may feel burdensome to new users.
- HPC communities have established norms around batch processing, optimisation, and system stewardship. Introducing cloud-native approaches challenges these norms and may be seen as destabilising ‘true’ HPC practice. This cultural friction can impede interoperability or create barriers to hybrid models.

5.2.3. Example 3: Digital Humanities and DRIs

Context:

Within the digital humanities community, researchers increasingly rely on DRI to support a variety of computational methods. However, the field is characterised by two distinct analytical cultures. One group uses DRI for automated, compute-intensive workflows, often requiring high-performance GPUs for tasks such as machine learning, large-scale text analysis, or image processing. The other group depends on iterative, researcher-guided workflows that require frequent user interaction, interpretive input, and exploratory refinement. Despite this diversity of practice, many DRIs remain optimised for automated processes. This structural orientation can unintentionally privilege one group over the other. As a result, gaps emerge in how different digital humanities communities experience access, support, and methodological legitimacy.

Points of friction:

- Automated-workflow users benefit from predictable GPU allocation and batch-style processing, while interactive-analysis users face challenges such as session timeouts, limited interface flexibility, or unstable interactive environments. These differences can affect who can work efficiently within the infrastructure.
- High-GPU users prioritise throughput, optimisation, and resource scalability. Interactive users prioritise responsiveness, usability, and ease of engagement. These differing priorities influence requests, interface expectations, and perceptions of what is relevant for the community.
- Users conducting automated workflows require assistance with GPU scaling, containerisation, and performance tuning. Interactive users need guidance on interface design, workflow integration, and iterative analysis support.

- Automated methods often align with the computational logic underlying modern DRIs, which can create an implicit hierarchy: GPU-intensive work appears more 'infrastructure-appropriate' than interpretive and interactive digital humanities methods. This can lead to feelings of marginalisation among researchers who rely on iterative approaches.

5.2.4. Example 4: Governing trust across epistemic cultures

Context:

Building a trusted national-level authentication and authorisation framework is challenging when organisations operate under very different regulatory and legal environments. Highly regulated sectors – such as the NHS, local government, and other public-service bodies – must comply with rigorous requirements around identity, access control, and data protection. A central question is whether a single Certificate Authority (CA) can provide sufficient trust for this full spectrum of organisations, or whether trust must be differentiated according to data sensitivity and regulatory obligations. Some organisations may hesitate to rely on certificates issued by a not-for-profit academic provider (e.g., Jisc), even if technically robust, because the provider's governance model or liability frameworks do not match their required standards. This raises the possibility that different communities may need multiple federations, each with its own trust models, assurance levels, and supporting technical services. If so, the next challenge is how these federations can interoperate smoothly to avoid fragmentation, inconsistent access, or duplicated infrastructure.

Points of friction:

- Organisations such as the NHS or local governments may be reluctant to rely on certificates issued by an academic sector CA. Their concerns may include compatibility with regulatory frameworks, questions about liability, differences in security posture, and the need for independently verifiable assurance levels. This can limit adoption or create pressure for alternative trust providers.
- Academic institutions, healthcare providers, and local authorities operate under different legislation, oversight structures, and risk tolerances. A single trust framework may be too rigid or too permissive depending on perspective, creating difficulty in agreeing on a shared assurance baseline.
- If multiple federations exist, users and services must still interact. Ensuring interoperability across different policy frameworks, authentication protocols, and trust anchors becomes technically and organisationally complex.

- Multiple trust models may lead to inconsistent login flows, variable access rights, or unclear expectations across services. This inconsistency can create confusion for users, hinder cross-sector collaboration, and reduce trust in the overarching infrastructure.

5.2.5. Example 5: DRI maturity and culture

Context:

Within the Arts and Humanities (A&H), research infrastructures vary widely in maturity, scale, and orientation. Long-established services – such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) at the University of York, with more than 30 years of operation and a staff of around 40 – have built business models shaped by extensive engagement with industry, particularly the construction sector, which provides 80–90% of ADS’s data inputs. These infrastructures operate in environments where sustainability, service provision, and professional compliance are central. By contrast, newly created DRIs in A&H tend to be smaller, more academically focused, and oriented around experimental or emerging research practices. Their priorities often centre on scholarly innovation and interdisciplinary experimentation rather than long-term service provision to industry. These differing histories and business models create cultural divergences that influence expectations around governance, sustainability, service design, user engagement, and the role of DRIs within the wider A&H landscape.

Points of friction:

- Long-standing infrastructures have decades of institutional memory, established workflows, and defined operational models, while newer DRIs are still forming their identity and processes. These different starting points create contrasting assumptions about what an infrastructure should prioritise and how it should operate.
- Services like ADS, shaped by industry contracts and regulatory compliance, prioritise stability, professional standards, and long-term preservation. Newer academic DRIs often rely on grant funding, emphasising innovation, flexibility, and research-driven development. These business model differences lead to contrasting incentives and expectations.
- Industry-aligned infrastructures must deliver predictable, compliant, and standardised services, while academic-oriented infrastructures prioritise experimentation, customisation, and exploratory research. This divide affects decisions about feature development, turnaround times, user support, and acceptable levels of risk.

- Industry-aligned infrastructures operate with strong service-delivery cultures, while academic DRIs often operate with more informal or research-driven cultures. These differences shape attitudes toward documentation, quality assurance, sustainability planning, and compliance.
- For long-established services, success may mean stability, reliability, and meeting regulatory obligations. For new DRIs, success may involve innovation, research impact, or piloting new methods.

5.2.6. Example 6: University structures and DRI mission

Context:

DRIs hosted within universities often face structural and organisational tensions due to their outward-facing missions. Whereas they are designed to support national or cross-institutional communities, they remain embedded within internal university systems, which prioritise departmental boundaries and institutional mandates. This incompatibility can create long-term instability. DRIs – especially newly created – may be moved between faculties, departments, or administrative units as leadership, strategic priorities, or funding structures shift. Each move introduces administrative burdens, disrupts workflows, and may threaten the continuity of services that external users depend on. This instability poses risks to digital services that require long-term persistence – such as persistent identifiers, data registries, and research-software services – where continuity and reliability are essential to maintaining user trust. The challenges highlight the need for more stable and explicit governance models capable of supporting DRIs that operate across institutional boundaries and serve wider communities beyond their host university.

Points of friction:

- DRIs are designed to serve national and cross-institutional research communities, yet university governance often emphasises internal priorities and departmental silos. This can constrain a DRI's ability to collaborate externally or scale services effectively.
- As DRIs – especially newly created – move between departments or administrative units – sometimes multiple times – they face repeated changes in oversight, reporting structures, financial processes, and service expectations. These moves disrupt operations and create inefficiencies that undermine long-term planning.
- Repeated migrations can endanger critical services such as persistent identifiers, which require stable governance, consistent URLs, and reliable hosting arrangements. Disruptions, even minor ones, erode trust among users who depend on long-term persistence.

- Departments often prioritise local teaching or research needs, whereas DRIs must prioritise national service delivery, interoperability, and sustainability. These competing priorities can lead to under-resourcing or strategic tensions.
- Every administrative move requires updated agreements, new processes, system reconfiguration, and renegotiation of responsibilities. This creates operational overhead for DRI staff and confusion for external users.

5.2.7. Example 7: Diverging norms around prestige and recognition

Context:

Across research communities that rely on DRIs, academic practices and norms of recognition are evolving in different ways. Whereas some disciplines continue to value traditional academic outputs – especially peer-reviewed journal publications – others are focusing on other forms of engagement and recognition. Within the HPC community, for example, formal publications are becoming less central. Instead, impactful presentations at major conferences, effective communication of technical contributions, and high-quality dissemination to practitioner audiences are increasingly valued markers of success. As DRIs foster more interdisciplinary collaboration, researchers encounter widely differing expectations around what counts as meaningful contribution, success, or academic credit. These incompatible norms introduce cultural complexity into collaborative work, affecting how individuals position their roles, justify their contributions, and meet the varying standards used by different communities. This variation creates challenges for the national federation of DRIs, which must support researchers working across diverse cultures of knowledge production and recognition.

Points of friction:

- When researchers, data professionals or practitioners from different communities work together via DRIs, they may judge success by incompatible standards. For example, one group may expect papers, while another sees conference presentations as more impactful.
- If one community rewards publication outputs and another rewards conference artefacts or performance-driven demonstrations, interdisciplinary researchers may struggle to satisfy both. This can create uncertainty around career development and recognition.
- A federation that spans multiple academic cultures must accommodate diverse norms without privileging one domain's standards over another's. Tensions around recognition and success can complicate governance, funding allocation, and expectations for cross-infrastructure collaboration.

5.2.8. Example 8: Cultures of data sharing in Heritage Science

Context:

Museums and cultural-heritage institutions are at an early stage of engaging with open data practices, and many are not yet accustomed to sharing collections information beyond their local systems. Unlike domains where open data exchange has become a norm, there is currently no widely accepted expectation that museum object data should be openly shared or federated across institutions. As a result, the shift toward participating in a federated DRI represents a significant cultural change for the sector. The absence of a shared understanding of the ‘public good’ that might arise from openly sharing cultural object information further complicates adoption. Many museums also face practical constraints: limited technical capacity, organisational readiness, and reduced staffing levels. With staff cuts across museums and galleries, upskilling collection teams to engage fully in federated DRI initiatives is understandably not a priority. This combination of cultural reluctance, lack of common practice, and organisational constraints presents substantial challenges for integrating museums into a national federation of DRIs.

Points of friction:

- Many institutions lack a unifying view of the societal or research benefits that could arise from openly sharing cultural object information. Without a clear sense of value, investment in open practices can seem unnecessary with institutional priorities.
- A significant number of museums are not yet equipped – technically or organisationally – to provide interoperable, standards-aligned collections data. Variability in cataloguing systems, data formats, and digital maturity impedes meaningful participation in federated infrastructures.
- Cuts across the museum and gallery sector reduce the time and resources available for upskilling. Without dedicated staff capacity, participating in federated DRI initiatives becomes difficult, slowing adoption and creating unequal engagement across institutions.
- Federated DRIs operate on openness, interoperability, and cross-institutional collaboration – principles that contrast with the more local, inward-facing operational models common in museums. Aligning these differing cultures requires significant organisational change.

5.3. Six themes–tensions along two axes

As mentioned before, the examples above come from the interviews. We have grouped them – together with other relevant issues – into six themes–tensions along two axes. The first axis is *power*, which includes the tension – or controversy – between centralisation versus decentralisation, visibility versus invisibility, and privacy versus surveillance/privatisation. The second is the *epistemic axis*, which includes the tension between empowerment versus disempowerment, certainty versus uncertainty and unity versus disunity. In what follows, the six themes–tensions are presented including evidence from interviews in the form of user narratives.

5.3.1. Power axis

Centralisation versus decentralisation

The creation of a national federation of DRIs will require a fundamental reorganisation of infrastructures, technologies, and data practices. This reorganisation has the potential to reestablish *trust* and create more coherent systems across the research landscape. However, it also exposes a fundamental cultural tension between centralised coordination – which includes the coordination guided by both big tech or government – and decentralised autonomy.

Centralisation promises consistent governance, unified technical standards, and harmonised data practices. It can simplify interoperability and ensure predictable levels of service across institutions. Yet centralisation may also raise concerns about loss of local control, diminished disciplinary autonomy, or the concentration of authority in national-level bodies.

Conversely, decentralisation supports diversity, disciplinary specificity, and local governance models that reflect the unique needs of different communities (academia, public sector and industry). But decentralised approaches can lead to fragmentation, uneven data practices, and challenges in maintaining cross-institutional trust.

At the centre of this tension lies questions about knowledge, authority, and expertise:

- Who is trusted to make authoritative decisions about data standards, technical architecture, or methodological validity?
- How should expertise be recognised across disciplinary boundaries with different norms, priorities, and epistemic cultures?

- How can trust be built when individuals must rely on knowledge, tools, and decisions coming from outside their own disciplinary expertise?

These questions intersect with issues of *governance* (participation and inclusion), *management* (workflow organisation), and *inter-institutional coordination* (levels of integration). These issues must be addressed by a better understanding of the opportunities and challenges that arise from both centralised and decentralised models.

The resulting tension is not simply technical or organisational, it is cultural. It reflects differing expectations about how decisions are made, who holds authority, and how *trust* can be sustained in a system that spans disciplines, institutions, and forms of expertise.

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

According to one participant, federation – for some users – is:

“(…) the necessary **evil** to gain access to compute resources.” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

If federation is seen this way – as the representation of a particular sociotechnical imaginary – this implies that federation necessarily requires the reorganisation of **trust** among different types of users across sectors, as this participant describes:

“The UK has at least 100 TREs, almost certainly more, so **if they all want to be able to play together then they've all got to trust each other**. And how do you enable that? You need some **governance structure** across the federation.” (Public Sector / Infrastructure Provider).

In this sense, federation is not only about providing access but also about building trust across communities with different epistemic cultures.

This issue of trust is further complicated by the fact that some users view federation not only as gaining access to compute resources but also to **data**. If one idea is shared by most interviewees is that the federation of compute resources is inseparable from the federation of data. One participant from industry emphasised this point clearly:

“I personally think about it [federation] much more in terms of what **access you have to the data** and then how you're going to interact with it rather than whether you're doing that a national or international or a local scale (...) to be honest, I **genuinely don't think about it in terms of where or what area the network covers or what scope is in.**” (Industry / Small Size)

If federation is about data, the focus should be on security and management, as this user highlights:

“Generally, I think the governance that needs to be focused in on is more of the **security** side of things and the trusted research environments and the data. So, **governance over the data and sharing the data** for me is where the focus should be on.” (Industry)

This understanding of federation is reinforced by another user who believes that federation is about the alignment of interests across sectors and disciplines – rather than an issue between public and private models:

“I would say for me the complexity is not between private and public; it's more **question of alignment of interest.**” (Industry)

What is interesting about these views is that they represent a user position which prioritises access over organisational structures – or accessibility over a more nuanced understanding of the ‘common good’ or the ‘power dynamics’ driving the national federation of DRIs.

However, this 'evil' entity is sometimes understood as extending beyond issues of access or technical constraints to include governance and power structures:

“The Federated system would obviously provide the basis for good big data management and analytics, but it **also creates the infrastructure for a lot of bad actors**, right? So, I think that the question for AI is not about whether computing data, access, to all kinds of pools of data or silos of data warehouses, it is not a question whether it can be done, because it's already been done. **It's about the policy framework around check and balances and who really governs the use and whether the public has a voice to say no.**” (NHS)

In this context, for this participant, federation:

“(…) evokes a certain kind of **decentralisation** which is appealing. It has a certain kind of **shared responsibility or mutualization of responsibility** with regard to different systems. So that's appealing” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

However, other users see federation as, and it is expected to be, a **centralised** system – closer to this 'evil' entity – either a centralised government or a big tech monopoly. This position is informed by differing views about who holds power and data governance.

Firstly, there is the question of power as the federation is established and becomes operational. For this participant from the public sector, real power sits – and will likely continue to sit – with the universities that host DRI and the funders:

“So, I think some of **the power will sit there** [universities that host DRIs], but I think primarily it's going to be around the **funders**. They will be guiding us to what is

excellent science for them, and that's that partly a political decision, but equally it is down to things like UKRI, they're going to be the ones who are really guiding us on what represents excellent science. So, **the real power brokers will be the funders rather than the communities.**" (Public Sector / Research Organisation)"

This view is not isolated – the next two quotations provide a similar perspective. This participant from academia states:

"if our core funding comes from the UKRI and as does a whole bunch of other DRI then really, it's the **UKRI who have mandating how we federate and the way that they want to go about it.** They're obviously pulling our opinions into it, but that the power disparity does then fall to them rather than us. And because many of these organisations are dependent on that funding to be able to operate, they don't have a full say in how much they will or will not federate." (Academia / Digital Humanities)

This participant from the public sector highlights:

"it's **the people managing the infrastructure that definitely hold the power.** If you, if you want to put it that way. So, they control the systems, the services, the types of solutions." (Public Sector / Historic Environment Scotland)

This participant provides a good example of these power dynamics:

“So, there was a very loose sense of federation like a technical topic. I think in part because of the **top-down emphasis on federation from the funding**. Instruments like the network plus [emerged] to respond to these more directive top-down conceptions of what DRI should be. That's what's put federation in our kind of like peripheral vision and then, I suppose, increasingly it seems like an important element of one secures access to a system, especially when you're part of a relatively marginal community.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Based on these considerations, this means that regardless of the governance model or the attempts to decentralise or distribute power, the federation will essentially be driven by the interests of some universities and funders – i.e., it will inevitably be centralised due to the existing – and very often underlying – power dynamics. However, one way to counterbalance these power relations is by including more voices in the governance structure, as this participant put it:

“Where is the voice of the people? Because we talk about **public voice** in our healthcare projects all the time, it's a primary importance that the public and the patient have an input into what kind of healthcare services are designed for them and made available to them. **But where is the public voice in this federated project?**” (Participant 11 – NHS)

Secondly, there is the question of who provides access – authentication and authorisation – to compute resources and data. In this context, federation is expected to be a **centralised system** because it requires centralised processes of authentication, authorisation, and accountability:

“the core technical piece of any sort of federated compute is some kind of **centralised triple A**, so

authentication, authorization, and accounting”. (Public Sector)

One form of centralisation of key federation processes is, for example, the introduction of a national user ID, as this user explains:

“Can I use these resources? That's when typically the resource provider will say well, you know you need to pay or, are you a member of a particular project who has paid? So maybe that's an angle actually that could be a useful thing. You know, **if you're authenticating using a single kind of national user ID you could automatically be joined to user groups, communities have already paid to access particular resources.** That would simplify matters a lot” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

Yet for users in the public sector, providing data access is “tricky”, particularly in relation to the scope and scale of permissions:

“if you host all your data in one place, in a cloud solution or a data lake, **how do you give the relevant access and permissions for different people or partners** where they sit around place around specific cohorts? And that's a tricky bit of federation for us. So, we have all these different individual silos and we want to put them all in the central place. But **we can't give everybody access to everything all the time for something.** It won't be appropriate or legal, actually to do so.” (Public sector / Local Authority)

This tension – the existence of a single authority that provides access – is clearly described by this user:

“Is it possible actually to have one central research Certification Authority that covers if you like, both ends of the sensitive data spectrum? Would NHS service managers, IT service managers, be happy to trust certificates signed, say by Jisc, if Jisc run a Central federation certification authority? Would that be enough for the NHS to trust? Would that be true for the NHS, for UK governments, Department of Work and Pensions, perhaps. HMRC, would it be sufficient for? I don't know.” (Public Sector / Infrastructure Provider).

That is, at some point, federation inevitably involves some form of power delegation – i.e., centralisation:

“There is nothing worse than rules that you cannot understand, and things that you cannot access. So, if you want to federate, it means basically delegate power on decision. Everything has to be crystal clear: who is taking your decision, what are the rules, what do I give up in term of ownership on what I would get here as a trade-off.” (Industry)

In sum, the tension between centralisation and decentralisation must be understood by examining issues of power and governance, along with issues of data accessibility, security, and more. Yet at the core of this tension lies *inclusion* and *trust*. Whether the system is centralised, decentralised, or positioned somewhere in between, the key question is how federation will ensure inclusion and (re)establish trust. In other words, the choice between centralisation and decentralisation is not neutral; it will shape the strategies through which inclusion and trust is built.

Visibility versus invisibility

The creation of a national federation of DRIs will introduce a fundamental tension between what becomes visible and what becomes invisible within the ecosystem. As infrastructures and technologies are potentially repurposed and reorganised (e.g., access and operation), some epistemic practices, forms of work, expertise and communities may become more visible, while others risk being marginalised or excluded.

Federation has the potential to recognise and reward certain actors – such as well-resourced institutions, established infrastructures, or communities aligned with dominant technical standards – making their practices highly visible across the national landscape. At the same time, the federation may unintentionally render other groups invisible by overlooking their assumptions, needs or contributions.

Forms of invisibility can emerge and become ‘normal’ for social reasons (e.g., under-resourced institutions, precarious contracts), material reasons (e.g., lack of interoperable technologies), or symbolic reasons (e.g., disciplinary hierarchies and collaboration architectures that privilege some types of knowledge over others).

These dynamics affect access, participation, recognition and awareness. Communities with fewer resources or lower institutional visibility may struggle to engage meaningfully, contributing to unequal adoption of the federation and reproducing existing inequalities across the research landscape.

Yet the tension is complicated by the fact that some forms of invisibility are considered ‘desirable’. Thus, ‘efficient’ infrastructures are often expected to remain invisible, thus enabling adoption, reducing cognitive load on users, and vanishing into the background of everyday epistemic practices. This ‘invisibility’ supports usability and lowers barriers to engagement.

This tension – between making things visible and keeping them invisible – is central to building a federation that is both technically viable and socially and culturally fair.

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

As mentioned above, a key concern among users is how federation might create the conditions for new forms of invisibility or expand existing ones. Drawing on interview

participants, at least three forms of invisibility may emerge in this context: (1) practices; (2) voices; and (3) needs.

Federation is expected to create **extra work** – e.g., new ways of authenticating, authorising and accessing compute resources and data for both providers and users. This participant describes this situation in a clear way:

“I know that some resource providers who offer compute resources, say, why should I bother being part of the federation? **It's just a load of extra work** and we do find just as we are by authenticating our own users in the way that we do it, as we've always done it, right? So, I don't see a need for federation.” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

The anticipation of additional work may lead to lower adoption of federated resources, or even a resistance to federation in general. However, the issue extends beyond extra workload; it also involves the lack of recognition of essential practices that sustain DRI development. For example, a key task within the DRI ecosystem is the maintenance of infrastructures (such as persistent identifiers) and the support provided to users and service providers. These practices are rarely acknowledged, which contributes to their invisibility. This issue is well described by the following user:

“Universities are working on a model of you do a research project and then you know, you finish the research project, and you move on and you do another one. Whereas **the DRI isn't so much about producing new research, it's about maintaining and supporting the research that others are doing. And that doesn't always get much recognition.**” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

A lack of recognition underpins several forms of invisibility. Regarding which **voices** are included or excluded within the DRI ecosystem, a clear divide exists between academic and non-academic contributors, even within universities. As one participant noted, the

“academic voice is considerably more powerful”, which means that other voices often go unheard and become increasingly invisible:

“They [people leading federation] talk about federation of things, but that all seems to be happening somewhere else and we get snippets and it's really hard to see what they're actually doing and it's very hard to understand where they're going with that work. So, I sort of know about it, but I don't really have a clear picture of it and **I'm not really a voice in that space.** There's a couple of reasons. One is that I am quite locally focused (...) But also, **I am non-academic.** One of the effects of that is that I cannot be a PI on a funded project. One of the effects of that is that I am not leading pieces of work that are contributing to these conversations (...) **the academic voice is considerably more powerful within my institution.**” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

“The academic voice is considerably more powerful” both within and beyond universities. This dynamic is recognised by the following user, who argues that federation is predominantly an academic project – defined largely by universities and research organisations – which creates the conditions for the exclusion of, for example, museums, galleries, libraries, and similar institutions:

“It's tempting to define **the boundaries of the federation just based on higher education institutions and the independent research organisations,** but there are many, many like, you know, hundreds of, if not thousands of kind of museums, collections, galleries, libraries and so on who don't have the status of independent research organization, who aren't part of

the technical federations that the higher education universe predicates that need to be included or otherwise would not get access to a federation if it was defined narrowly.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

This is echoed by people who work with museums and galleries. The following participant articulates their feelings about this situation particularly well:

“We're not in any way central to the discussions and central to the conversations [about federation] is our feeling that we had when we left [the DRI congress] to be honest (...) And I think in the session that we gave talks alongside colleagues from similar kind of projects, it was really good to have our voice heard and demonstrate the impact we can deliver. But, I **don't think we're central to the conversations.**” (Public Sector / Collection Trust)

This feeling of “exclusion” is concerning. It renders some communities invisible and causes them to gradually lose the capacity and motivation to shape, influence or question key aspects of federated infrastructure design, thereby narrowing the epistemic values, norms, and modes of reasoning that underpin federation.

Another aspect of invisibility concerns the way certain user or community **needs** are unacknowledged. In the case of users from the arts and humanities, this issue is more complex: they often lack both the mindset and the support needed to participate effectively in a federated system. The following participant describes this challenge clearly:

“they [people in arts and humanities] don't have the **Technical Support** that colleagues in the sciences have. So, I do a bit of work around greening digital research and making it less environmentally impactful and we've been looking at various kind of certification

schemes and it's fascinating because **the certification schemes are being taken up very rapidly and very successfully in the sciences, but hardly at all in the humanities.** And it's because the sciences have infrastructure where technicians and lab staff can pick up the knowledge about that stuff and then bring it into their labs. Whereas in the arts and humanities, it has to be the researcher again has to find the headspace and the time to learn about that and to adapt their practices. So, **we're finding it really difficult to bring those practices into arts and humanities simply because of the different structural setup,** where it's sort of single researchers leading projects that might employ some postdocs but are not relying on a permanent technician or you know it's permanent resource within the university to support them.”
(Academia / Digital Humanities)

In the case of users from the public sector, their needs also tend to be invisible within federation – or within the logic underpinning the development of national federated compute services. Potential users may struggle to understand and align their interests with those of, for example, HPC institutions, as the following participant explains:

“High performance computing institutions are set up for relatively small user bases, you know of researchers, highly technical user bases. Data scientists in the public sector might be pretty similar to that audience and might find the sort of support offering adequate, but **for wider groups like analysts in government, you know statisticians or economists the kind of Technical Support needed and the number of them are going to**

be higher than the kind of user base that high performance computing facilities are set up for. So, you can't necessarily expect the same support offering with things like, you know, lost passwords and you know, unexpected behaviour of a particular application that you might get from a public cloud provider.”
(Public sector / Central Gov).

These forms of invisibility are diverse and become increasingly complex in the context of DRI federation. Likewise, the reasons behind the emergence and persistence of these practices are multilayered. Based on interviewee accounts, we have organised these reasons into two categories: material and symbolic differences.

For example, participant 4 from academia (digital humanities) describes how longstanding funding inequalities among disciplines may be overlooked in the context of federation:

“An inclusive DRI needs to **recognise funding inequalities that are historic** (...) If you don't compensate for those historic, let's say, under investment and DRI, you're not going to get inclusive access because you'll find things like skills gaps or whatever lack of understanding of what's possible (...) so to what extent is that legacy being informing the levels of engagement now? (...) **If you don't compensate for those historic, let's say under investment and DRI, you're not going to get inclusive access** because you'll find things like skills gaps or whatever lack of understanding of what's possible (...)” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Participant 5 explains how work instability affects the maintenance of DRIs:

“The DRI isn't so much about producing new research, it's about maintaining and supporting the research that others are doing (...) [yet] It's often not funded properly as a maintenance exercise. It's funded on a project basis, which is very stressful. **I am always on a fixed-term contract**, for example, and I just have to hope that we are able to get, you know, more funding to continue and **it makes it very difficult to plan for the future because you don't know if you're going to be able to keep your people.**” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

These material differences have an impact on how some users engage – understand, use and benefit – with DRIs:

“Take an HPC, for example. If Hartree Centre was going to allow Federated academic users onto the platform, **they would be much lower priority compared to paying private sector company.** You basically **partition the system** so that the paying customers have priority and access to all of this, and then if there's any, like, backfill anything leftover at the end, then we can perhaps allocate that to your Federated users.” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

In other words, the federated system risks becoming partitioned according to institutions' capacity to pay for resources. This is also evident in the situation of small institutions that lack the necessary resources to join a federated system, as this user noted:

“I do feel sorry for the groups that are much smaller because they can only achieve much smaller gains. So hopefully you know there is a thought process that

federation might be able to address that, but I don't know how that would work.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

In some sectors, this lack of resources means that federation is not considered a real priority:

“Staff are being cut in lots of museums and galleries, so **upskilling collection staff to fully engage in digital research infrastructure is not a priority, absolutely not a priority.**” (Public Sector / Collection Trust).

But it is not only about material but also about **symbolic conditions**, or a combination of both. For example, Participant 2 from the public sector emphasises that access to systems is shaped by subtle factors such as networking or proximity to certain groups:

“There's a lot of cases where you can get **access to systems** because you know people and that **networking**, I think, is always going to play some level of importance (...)” (Public Sector / Research Organisation)

Participant 8 emphasises this aspect, particularly for users from communities that feel 'excluded' – the point, again, is to know who the right person is to get access, a capacity that is unequally distributed among users:

“The mechanics of access, which often feel like you have to already be using it to know how to access it. Even you know internally there's often a sense that something looks quite hard to access. There's waiting lists, there's big costs, but if you talk to “John”, he knows how to get you in for free. **It feels very much like you need to know and be talking to the right people to**

understand what's available.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

In the same line but from a different perspective, what is at play here is research culture – i.e., the ways in which research is valued and enacted:

“I think we have a research culture in this country which discourages that and encourages individual focus on certain kinds of outputs and the next bid and the next bid (...) so there's not a strong culture of support and community around research, and that might be changing a bit, but it's not there yet.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

However, for some users, **federation is about invisibility** – i.e., the success of federated DRIs relies on making infrastructure invisible. Participant 12 from the public sector explains this clearly:

“Ideally much of federation should be hidden from the user (...) hiding as much as possible behind the scenes I think is something that everybody in the Federation Compute services world has a duty that seems a bit hard, isn't it? But everyone should try and make it as invisible as possible” (Public Sector / Infrastructure Provider)

Participant 5 from industry has a similar position:

“Users would have access to systems. It doesn't matter where that system would be in the UK, but they would have access and that system would drive their science most efficiently. They would have a single portal to

access that system, but it doesn't matter where that is geographically. So, **federation is the infrastructure behind it. The user shouldn't care what the federation looks like.** All they should really be doing is understanding where the best resource is for this".
(Industry / Medium-large Size)

In sum, the tension between invisibility and visibility in DRI federation has to do with the process of becoming invisible, and the mechanisms required to prevent harm or unequal benefits resulting from the exclusion of particular practices, voices, and needs.

Privacy versus surveillance/privatisation

The federation of DRIs will require national – and eventually international – coordination among public and private actors. This raises questions about ownership, not only in the present or near future but also over the long term, and not only ownership of services but also of data. In particular, data privacy may be at risk in a funding environment where infrastructures face financial pressures. Some national or institutional actors may view data assets – especially sensitive datasets – as candidates for monetisation to support operational costs. Monetisation pressures can erode traditional commitments to academic openness and public benefit, potentially shifting the federation toward commercial logic. This can blur boundaries between legitimate cost recovery and forms of privatisation that restrict data access or introduce market-driven surveillance practices.

The federation will also demand new mechanisms for authenticating and authorising access to compute resources, services, and datasets. Potentially, this means the introduction of a national-scale digital identity, where researchers, data professionals, practitioners, institutions, and infrastructures must verify who is accessing what, under which conditions. While essential for security and coordinated access, these identity systems can also create new opportunities for surveillance. Centralised credential systems may record detailed traces of user behaviour – queries, datasets accessed, workflows executed, technologies used – raising concerns about who can see this information, how it is governed, and whether it might be used in ways that exceed its original goal.

At stake are key questions about governance, trust, and the protection of academic freedom:

- Who controls – and will control – the data?

- How transparent are monitoring and logging practices?
- What safeguards prevent the drift from necessary security toward intrusive tracking?
- How can the federation prevent financial pressures from leading to the commercialisation of access to public-good data infrastructures?

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

Participant 11 from NHS describes what is at play as federation of DRIs evolves within a ‘capitalist model’ of knowledge production:

“This is probably in a kind of a **capitalist model**, right? So, you look at Google, Facebook, you know, even Amazon data, you know, they're all very, very large. And in the end, **they will come in and buy up all these so-called data warehouses**. This is a real capitalist game [...] But then at one point when the Secure Data Environment (SDE) needs to survive because government runs out of money, **they will sell it to the big data companies** [...] So when that happens, how do you make up those tax receipts? By breaking up juicy parts of the healthcare system that big data companies want to buy, you know, and the SDE is one of them.”
(NHS)

However, relationships with these large technology companies are not a future possibility – they are already taking shape, bringing with them multiple challenges, as this participant describes:

“We're engaging with some of those big players. So, for example, **we went to see Amazon last year and the**

stuff that they could do using their AI was just phenomenal when it would save loads of time and money. So, we understand the opportunity absolutely, but we had more responsibility around how we use people's data because of the subject matter of it [...] If we choose as a statutory body or a public body responsible for your care and health or your well-being, and we make the wrong decision, that's really bad news. But again, I guess it comes back as that concept proportionality for me again [...]" (Public Sector / Local Authority)

The federation must take into account how different users – active, potential, and inactive – interact with big tech companies. For instance, Participant 4, from academia, draws attention to the risks associated with 'masking' these relationships:

"so, while there will be state-funded compute facilities, some of these will be somehow abstracted away into the cloud providers that are sort of exactly the kinds of commercial relationships that we're trying to at least educate people about, so I'm interested in how federation can sort of mask the ultimate provider of compute." (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Yet it seems that most people do not think or care about these relationships – this participant questions how these interactions are at some point ignored:

"Who stores their data, and who uses it? You're getting into quite obscure questions at this point, right? (...) it's like I'd be happy for it to be used by, I don't know, UK companies, but not companies outside the UK, would that be a legitimate or I'd be happy for it to be used by

companies in the UK and the EU, but not in the US (...) most people don't care much about that stuff, most people don't think about it.” (Industry)

The way these relationships are embedded in some HPC facilities, and its potential consequences are described by this participant:

“if the cost of computer resources is often shared by multiple people from multiple organisations and so on, there are, I mean, and this is true, **there are instances when a private sector company wants to reserve a slice of that or all of that resource and not share it with anybody**, you know, for a certain period, and then when they're done, everything gets scrubbed. So, sharing it at the same time with the federation of other users who are using the system causes kind of **security concerns**. You know concerns some private sector companies say, ‘oh no, we're not going to be sharing the resource with a load of other Federated people, we need dedicated resource because I have to protect our IP’.” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

The presence of private companies in the public sector is also concerning for some people – it reconfigures trust relationships, especially among councils:

“**Social Care** is a very different sector to the NHS and it's predominantly **private sector provision**. It's got a mix of suppliers from very large (...) to absolutely minute, so you've got a real breadth of digital capabilities and skills in those providers and you've got a real difference because of the private sector lens to the NHS, which is quite public sector (...) So, all of that

means that **there's actually some challenges around levels of trust about sharing the data.**" (Public Sector / Local Authority)

These multiple concerns – privatisation, commercialisation, transparency, and security – are manifestations of emerging forms of interaction with private technology companies.

Beyond these issues, some users raise an additional concern that merits further attention: **surveillance**. This concern is closely connected to the need for digital identities to participate in the federation. As one participant explains:

"I think it's going to be something similar to this kind of idea about **national ID cards**, virtual ID cards (...) there's going to be a lot of **resistance** to that because people don't like being checked upon. They **don't like being recorded** and anonymity is protecting your data or that kind of thing is a big topic. So, I think they would culturally, there could be resistance to any kind of endeavours to do this properly this kind of National scale." (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

Therefore, within the context of data commercialisation and privatisation, alongside competitive pressures in research such as publications and citations, future users may question:

(...) do I disclose any of my IP, any of **my research?** (...) [because] **they're watching you**" (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

In sum, this tension reflects power dynamics between public organisations and private companies, in particular, users' concerns about transparency, security, and surveillance. It is underpinned by future scenarios in which data ownership and individual privacy could be transformed in unforeseen ways.

5.3.2. Epistemic axis

Empowerment versus disempowerment

The establishment of a national federation of DRIs will demand new forms of accessibility, communication, coordination and collaboration across institutions, disciplines, and infrastructures. People's engagement with federation go beyond upskilling or retraining to include awareness of the opportunities, or what can be called *federation mindset* – a shift in how individuals and communities see themselves within the federation landscape, their roles, responsibilities, and professional identities.

Whereas this mindset has the potential to empower users, it can also create new forms of disempowerment if not supported appropriately. On one hand, participation in a federated system can empower researchers by giving them greater control over their data, enabling more seamless access to national resources, and supporting privacy through shared standards, robust governance, and transparent workflows. A well-implemented federation can strengthen professional autonomy by providing users with the confidence to navigate complex data environments safely and effectively.

On the other hand, without adequate support and recognition of disciplinary diversity, the federation mindset may lead to disempowerment. The shift requires not only technical skills but also significant professional identity (re)negotiation: users must adopt new collaborative norms, learn to trust systems beyond their home institution, and operate within governance frameworks that may feel distant or opaque. Those who lack institutional support, have limited time, or work in under-resourced environments may struggle to participate meaningfully, leaving them feeling marginalised or excluded.

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

Participant 5 from industry capture a key point when it comes to rethinking federated system from a social and cultural perspective – it is not about technology but about (empowering) people:

“Technology is done. You can federate technology.
Might have just challenges here and there. **Federating**

the people and joining the people together, I think is a key angle that we should look at as well (...) any federation would need to be interdisciplinary.” (Industry / Medium-large Size)

That is, it is not simply about more training on skills but awareness and inclusive forms of engagement, as this participant put it:

“Often the kind of the services that are offered are kind of like vanilla services, just vanilla compute, whether that be access to a command line, terminal for an HPC or access to a virtual desktop for a VRA, Jupiter, Python, kind of programming and scripting environment. I don't think that needs retraining. I just think it needs more awareness. And I think the issue basic for me is that.” (Public Sector / HPC facility)

Thus, awareness of new opportunities that leads to inclusive engagement seems to be crucial for some users who feel excluded from federation, or the HPC ecosystem. It is common for some users – mainly inactive ones – to feel confused as they engage with these systems even when they support, as this participant put it:

“The research team within our Information Services area, their job is to support people onto high performance compute. My experience when I have sent anyone to that team is that they cannot get into the same conversation. They come back feeling more confused.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

If they feel more confused, or they cannot “get into the same conversation” means that they are not empowered to engage properly – actively and critically – in federated systems.

Yet there are many ways to disempower users. Disempowerment may occur, for example, during moments of active engagement with the design or discussion of federated systems. For example, participant 8 from digital humanities describes how subtle forms of disempowerment happens due to disciplinary power imbalances in specific settings:

“I went to a digital research infrastructure conference not long ago. I was invited to go and talk from a humanities perspective, and we were talking about computes, and we were talking about data centres and various things like that. And at one point somebody turned around and asked me if I could follow the conversation. So, **there was a degree of very patronising attitude towards the arts and humanities as well**. So, it's interesting. I think that line between what is patronising and what is accessible is hard”
(Academia / Digital Humanities)

Participant 2 from industry points to something crucial when it comes to empowering users within any federated system – the need for a “sense of purpose, play and potential” among different types of users. It is about shared values and social norms rather than technology:

“A growth where they can bring their own expertise and do things together. This kind of behaviour should be encouraged, that there is a **bottom-up growth** rather than you know coming from the top because even if there is, even if there is, you know, a very smart person sitting at the top, that person would not collectively be wiser than everybody who is working at the bottom. So, it's important that there is some degree of control from the top but there is a much wider sense of movement from the people who are actually doing the things and they are collectively pushing it together. So yeah, I

would say a sense of creating a **sense of purpose**, creating a **sense of play**, creating a **sense of potential**, that's what I would do.” (Industry / Medium–large Size)

This “bottom–up growth” also involves a more decentralised approach to training. This participant captures the key point:

“I would like to see diverse training. Not one training, centralised training provider doing the courses that they do, but **diverse training for different types of people**. Different types of disciplines in different locations but easily navigable and attendable.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Therefore, the creation of a “federated mindset” needs to recognise the tension between empowerment and disempowerment. For example, empowerment requires the recognition of diverse epistemic cultures aiming to access and use federated resources. This means that a federated mindset can take multiple shapes, leading to multi-dimensional approaches to federation. In other words, this demands the constitution of a “bottom–up” empowerment infrastructure.

Certainty versus uncertainty

The development of a national federated infrastructure ecosystem is expected to rest on shared standards, protocols, and ontologies, thus providing greater certainty for both users and service providers. However, federation also introduces new forms of uncertainty: users must navigate shifting expectations, differences in communication styles, conflicting interests, evolving terminology, variations in technical language, and unfamiliar modes of coordination that shape how knowledge is produced. These uncertainties can lead to contrasting interpretations of roles and responsibilities, as well as what federation entails, what collaboration looks like, and how decisions should be made across contexts.

The challenge for the national federation is therefore to balance these competing needs and interests, misunderstandings and differing interpretations but now in a new scale. Too much emphasis on certainty risks imposing rigid structures that do not fit diverse disciplinary contexts; too much tolerance for uncertainty risks confusion, fragmentation, and loss of trust.

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

A key aspect of the tension between certainty and uncertainty in federated services and resources lies in what is known as “language barrier” across disciplines:

“So I feel that, you know, when you if you federate and you are sharing those resources, **there is a language barrier** and I don't mean, you know, English to Italian or anything like that, but more **across disciplines that is going to be difficult to accomplish** and it's going to take time and it's going to take patience I think to accomplish it.” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Even the meaning of DRI itself has been subject to communicative uncertainty, with inconsistent or unclear explanations circulating within the DRI ecosystem. One participant captures this ambiguity when describing their experience of the situation:

“Sometimes the way that DRI is used, I'm very **interested in how the phrase DRI is used in different contexts**, because increasingly I hear it used to be to mean just high performance compute (...) I wouldn't define it like that. **I would define it as all of the infrastructure that is required for digital research.**” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

However, this tension goes beyond language or communication barriers across distinct epistemic cultures and includes the negotiation of (sometimes unknown) interests. That is, there is growing uncertainty about what those leading the federation are seeking, as this participant explains:

“they [people running DRIs] are looking for diversity of user or diversity of user groups in order to show the value of the infrastructure, [and] bring more money into the infrastructure [...] **They don't want to hear that that's not working. What they want to hear is, 'oh, yes, here's something that's ready to fit into your pipeline' and we'll offer you this different user group...and it's quite an interesting tension that sort of interest, but lack of interest at the same time**” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

Such negotiations also arise when two distinct epistemic cultures are brought together and hold opposing views on, for example, open science. This participant offers an illustrative example:

“But you've got two very different cultures there. They [HPC community] are much more open, traditional HPC culture of open science. And the very closed world of trusted research environments and different approaches to risk. And this again is trust. But **these two very different cultures that you know, you're suddenly colliding.**” (Public Sector).

If federation involves scaling up services and resources, it also brings new forms of uncertainty regarding who will use particular technologies and data, and how they will be used. This is especially challenging for small communities that may suddenly become part of much larger groups – due to federation – seeking access to specific types of data, as this participant describes:

“now that large language model and AI have become such a big thing **all of a sudden our data has become a lot more valuable.** It seems a lot more in vogue because people want to have massive textual

data sets to be working with. And I think that has raised new challenges for us in terms of **what should we be doing about that?** So that's a new situation for us in terms of we're used to having a very small user base of people who either know we exist or there are people who don't and we we've kind of kept it that way because we're a very small team and we can't necessarily deal with a large user base.” (Academia – Digital Humanities)

And again, this is particularly difficult for some communities because:

“A lot of humanity scholars **have not really been trained to think of their research materials as data.**”
(Academia – Digital Humanities)

These user narratives show how certainty and uncertainty in federated services and resources emerges as a multidimensional challenge tied to *meaning-making*, *interests*, and *scale*. Whereas federation promises clarity through shared infrastructures and ontologies, it simultaneously generates uncertainty as diverse epistemic cultures interact, often with incompatible languages, assumptions, and norms.

Participants describe how even core concepts such as DRI lack shared definitions, leading to ambiguity about scope and purpose. This communicative uncertainty is intensified by poorly articulated institutional interests, particularly where federation leaders prioritise scalability in ways that may not align with community needs. Tensions intensify when federated services and resources bring together cultures with opposing approaches to openness, risk and governance – such as open HPC environments and secure data environments – requiring negotiations grounded in trust that is not always established.

Finally, as federation scales up access to data and technologies, it introduces new uncertainties around data use, ownership and capacity, especially for small or humanities-oriented communities unfamiliar with treating research materials as data, or managing large and external user bases. These dynamics are illustrative of federation as a process that redistributes and reconfigures uncertainty across actors, practices, and infrastructures.

Unity versus disunity

The development of a national federated infrastructure ecosystem requires the establishment of shared standards, protocols, and ontologies – a structured framework that defines the concepts, relationships, and rules within a specific domain. This means that federation will likely bring greater ‘unity’ across infrastructures, workflows, and, most importantly, data practices across sectors – i.e., federation promises a more coherent national research ecosystem.

However, as federated systems increasingly standardise aspects and processes of knowledge creation (including data analysis of different types), they may unintentionally narrow the *context and logic of discovery*. Standardisation inevitably privileges certain types of epistemologies, methodologies, and data practices. In other words, while federation seeks to enhance interoperability and efficiency, they may also reduce *epistemic diversity* – the plurality of ways in which different fields explore questions, build knowledge, and define valid evidence.

This reduction in epistemic diversity can manifest as a decline in epistemic cultures, especially in communities whose practices rely on interpretive, exploratory, or context-sensitive approaches. When infrastructures optimise for uniformity, they may exclude or marginalise knowledge traditions, data practices and requirements that do not align with standardised representations.

Below, some contrasting views are provided as evidence of this tension. These views are presented as user narratives that both challenge the current situation and anticipate possible future conditions.

User narratives

Federation involves the development of a ‘common ground’. Yet the key question is how much standardisation is needed to make national federated DRIs possible. For this participant from the public sector, federation is:

“probably not complete standardisation of things across all layers, but **standardisation of enough that there could be a decent flow of information across that whole sort of network**” (Public sector / Central Gov).

Although this vision remains too abstract, it is widely shared by most users. This user ascribes to this idea:

“we need to have all of these **strict rules**, but at the same time, how can you be **flexible** and work within your own infrastructure?” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

In other words, there is an understanding that a balanced set of standards are needed to allow “a decent flow of information across the network” but it seems difficult to define it concretely. What does it mean “enough standardisation” in this context? (Bowker & Star, 1999). What are the social, cultural and epistemic conditions for this “enoughness”? How will this “enoughness” be enacted by future users?

Beyond standardisation, participants also highlight the need for a more coherent ecosystem. For this participant, for example, federation involves necessarily the reduction of the number of *trusted research environments* (TREs):

“There should be **a small number of highly capable TREs** in the UK. **We don't need all these hundreds of them (...)** But if you connect them all together [federation] then the market will take care of the duplication (...) **the duplication of, say, research projects will be taken care of by the natural functioning of the market.**” (Public Sector / Infrastructure Provider)

This quote is particularly interesting because it articulates a vision of a future with fewer TREs, in which “the market will take care of duplication”. In the context of DRI, duplication is often understood as the existence of exact copies of data, files, datasets, and similar artifacts, which over time become a major burden on storage capacity, processing power, and system performance. Yet this participant referred to “the duplication of research projects”, which means the unnecessary repetition of research efforts. The idea that “the market” should “take care” of it points to a vision in which epistemic diversity is ultimately shaped by funding mechanisms and competitive dynamics.

Other participants see federation as a practice where users should use *shared software frameworks*. Thus, by standardising technical foundations across disciplines, federation is framed as enabling researchers and data professionals to focus on scientific inquiry rather than infrastructure, while ensuring that software tools carry consistent meaning and value across domains, as this user from industry put it:

“So, what we would like to see is people using the **software frameworks** which are already there to build an AI model of XYZ. Just use that framework and then let that researcher concentrate on the science that they're pushing forward. So, what they don't have to worry about the software, it's there and all they worry about is their research (...) **The software would have the same meaning and the same value to all the different disciplines.** The first layer of software, the layer above, might be domain specific, but that middle layer, if you can get people trained on that, understanding how the software can help them understanding everything else, **that would bring commonality across the different pillars of research**” (Industry / Medium–large Size).

Other users view federation as using a particular tool – e.g., Jupyter notebook:

“So, if tomorrow you will ask me, **how to build a federated service across different scientific communities?** I will go through **a Jupyter notebook**. You know, I would consider that every scientist or most of the scientists should be able to know to auto write code using a GPT Jupyter notebook on to deport the execution of that code on the big facility.” (Industry – Active user)

For this participant from the public sector, users across disciplines should be afforded the opportunity to use their traditional methods initially, while gradually moving toward a “common interface”:

“we're going to have to change our approach so the communities only have to learn particular infrastructures, and there may be a back door in for them to continue using the methods they're using (...) So I think the two will exist in parallel, but **gradually as the new or as the established communities start winding down, we'll start seeing more and more people turning towards this common interface.**” (Public Sector / HPC Facility).

At the centre of these processes of unification – TRES and software architectures – lies a question about users' *autonomy*. This participant highlights the main trade-off at play in the federation of DRIs:

“the sensitive data researchers are having to **shift their way of working** more towards the traditional HPC way of working [remote access model]. [This means that] a researcher is going to have to **give up some of the freedoms** that they have had to be able to work with the data that they want.” (Public Sector / Infrastructure Provider)

If perceptions of autonomy loss or gain are fundamental to federation, it follows that some users will “defend” these perceptions as part of their epistemic cultures. This raises the question of whether users will be willing to “sacrifice” some of their “freedoms” – “pay a price” – in order to participate in federated services and resources. The history of science and technology shows that individuals and scientific communities have often had to give up, detach from, or reform certain habits, ambitions, and self-relations to gain access to new technologies (Daston, 2023).

However, such processes of renunciation are typically accompanied with processes of “professional identity (re)negotiation” (Durán del Fierro et al., 2024; Littlejohn et al., 2026): reflections on what kind of science or data analysis they wish to pursue, and what it means to be a scientist, technologist or practitioner – i.e., it is not only an epistemological problem, but also ontological (here in a philosophical and sociological sense). These negotiations are crucial in enabling users to view these processes as *equipping* them with certain “privileges” – namely, proximity to specific groups that provide access to services and resources – rather than as *dispossessing* them (deskilling).

There are multiple reasons why some users perceive federation as a threat to autonomy and epistemic diversity. In particular, some users believe that the federation of data entails additional work for them:

“Are we going to have to change our standards again? How are we going to integrate that data? You know, we've been building up metadata standards and protocols for 25 years now, so, you know, there's an element there of difficultness in terms of moving that iceberg” (Academia / Digital Humanities).

Thus, there is the question of whether:

“Do we need to federate all this data? Is it really useful to be able to compare, you know, health data with particle physics data? (...) How do we, as an archaeology cultural heritage archive, link up with an archive that looks at languages, for example, and is that useful?” (Academia / Digital Humanities)

For other users, federation, despite offering access to new compute services and resources, is not perceived as a real necessity, as local compute centres already provide adequate solutions while preserving their sense of autonomy:

“The communities that I've been involved with a lot in the past, they're kind of self-served by their own

compute centres largely. So, they've never really seen a need to federate. They've got access to their own universities, HPC or, you know, a cluster or something like that.” (Public Sector / HPC Facility)

The maintenance of dedicated “standards” and “compute centres” allows some communities not only to safeguard their autonomy, but also to sustain forms of epistemic diversity that are grounded in discipline-specific practices, tools, and norms. In this sense, autonomy and epistemic diversity are not secondary concerns; they are actively valued by users and communities as conditions for doing credible work on their own terms and for protecting established ways of producing, validating and sharing knowledge.

But, at the same time, federation can provide new opportunities: a more coherent ecosystem in which users can draw on data and compute resources across multiple research environments and facilities, thereby streamlining approval processes and accelerating different types of analysis.

It is between this tension – expanding or constraining autonomy and epistemic diversity – that we can now understand why federation is sometimes framed as “*the necessary evil to gain access to compute resources*”. It is an “evil” that may provide opportunities but there is a price to be paid: the loss of autonomy – at an individual level – and the stretching of heterogeneity – at a collective level.

6. Concluding remarks

The six tensions across the two axes illustrate something crucial for the efforts behind the national federation of DRIs: the continual inclusion of users and sectors (epistemic diversity) depends on how power is distributed (centralisation versus decentralisation), and how users are empowered (awareness, negotiation and skills). Thus, inclusion – understood as an expansion of epistemic diversity – must be framed alongside logics of exclusion. Inclusion is inseparable from exclusion, since any social system, in order to develop and reproduce (that is, to survive), must regulate the extent of inclusion. This tension is a core dynamic in the national federation of digital research infrastructures (DRIs).

Drawing on social studies of science and technology, the inclusion/exclusion dynamics of a national federation of digital research infrastructures (DRIs) can be analysed through the concept of *boundaries*. This concept has been widely used to understand how professions establish demarcations – such as classification systems – to distinguish themselves from

others (Lamont & Molnár, 2002). Boundaries may be social, cultural, or symbolic, and they enable social systems to reduce environmental complexity and manage pressures from external actors seeking entry. As such, boundaries are not only mechanisms of division and exclusion, but also conditions for communication, collaboration, cooperation, exchange, and inclusion (Bowker & Star, 1999; Star & Griesemer, 1989).

The table below illustrates different future scenarios of inclusion in national federated DRIs, their corresponding boundaries, and how they affect user archetypes:

Levels – high to low	Description
Fully inclusive	All users open their laptop and are part of federation – inclusive but “oppressive” (there is not opt out).
Integrated inclusion	Inactive and potential users can join the federation if they comply with specific requirements – these requirements recognise work practices and values from diverse communities and sectors.
Partially inclusive	Inactive and potential users can join the federation if they comply with requirements – these requirements are decided by one community or discipline. New users must change their work practices and forms of communication to be part of it.
No inclusion	Inactive and potential users who want to join federation are not allowed – Active users who are not upskilled are excluded. Full automation.

Table 6. Levels of inclusion in DRI federation

The key question behind these scenarios is: who gains and losses if the national federation of DRIs develops homogenised standards for all the communities and sectors, or standards that vary from place to place, field to field, and practitioner to practitioner?

The degree of inclusion – and exclusion – depends on the mechanisms used to filter the complexity of epistemic cultures. What is at stake is not only the extent of inclusion that is anticipated, but also the kinds of boundaries that enable the integration of DRIs and their use by diverse epistemic communities. These boundaries can take multiple forms depending on their purpose: reducing complexity, enabling cultural permeability, facilitating translation without consensus, or making cross-boundary interaction predictable and meaningful.

A key tension concerns how standards (as boundary objects) are designed, governed, and enforced in order to make federation possible. If standards actively shape practice – if they create culture by requiring people to work in particular ways – then how they come into being becomes crucial. This raises questions about the level and form of participation required to design and implement standards, as well as the type of boundary work involved. This may include practices of alignment, the emergence of resistance, and the development of trading zones to negotiate disagreements or conflicts. The relationship between boundary work (how boundaries are strategically constructed and defended) and boundary objects (how actors coordinate across boundaries without dissolving them) is therefore fundamental to understanding the demands for integration, interdisciplinarity, and trust that national DRI federation brings.

Finally, as our interviews show, federation is understood in multiple ways: as a practical tool, a compliance requirement, a marker of institutional modernity, a “necessary evil”, or an unwanted burden. For others, federation carries symbolic significance, representing credibility or a sense of belonging within a wider scientific, professional, or technological community. These social, cultural, and symbolic differences shape how federation produces conditions for exclusion or, alternatively, for communication, exchange, cooperation, and inclusion.

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